

MAPK Pathway Activity - Normal Liver Atlas

p53 Pathway Activity - Normal Liver Atlas

MAPK Pathway Activity - TME-Stroma Atlas

p53 Pathway Activity - TME-Stroma Atlas

MAPK Pathway Activity - TME-Immune Atlas

p53 Pathway Activity - TME-Immune Atlas

JAK-STAT Pathway Activity - Normal Liver Atlas

NFkB Pathway Activity - Normal Liver Atlas

JAK-STAT Pathway Activity - TME-Stroma Atlas

NFkB Pathway Activity - TME-Stroma Atlas

JAK-STAT Pathway Activity - TME-Immune Atlas

NFkB Pathway Activity - TME-Immune Atlas

Hypoxia Pathway Activity - Normal Liver Atlas

PI3K Pathway Activity - Normal Liver Atlas

Hypoxia Pathway Activity - TME-Stroma Atlas

PI3K Pathway Activity - TME-Stroma Atlas

Hypoxia Pathway Activity - TME-Immune Atlas

PI3K Pathway Activity - TME-Immune Atlas

TGFb Pathway Activity - Normal Liver Atlas

TNFa Pathway Activity - Normal Liver Atlas

TGFb Pathway Activity - TME-Stroma Atlas

TNFa Pathway Activity - TME-Stroma Atlas

TGFb Pathway Activity - TME-Immune Atlas

TNFa Pathway Activity - TME-Immune Atlas

VEGF Pathway Activity - Normal Liver Atlas

Trail Pathway Activity - Normal Liver Atlas

VEGF Pathway Activity - TME-Stroma Atlas

Trail Pathway Activity - TME-Stroma Atlas

VEGF Pathway Activity - TME-Immune Atlas

Trail Pathway Activity - TME-Immune Atlas

Androgen Pathway Activity - Normal Liver Atlas

Estrogen Pathway Activity - Normal Liver Atlas

Androgen Pathway Activity - TME-Stroma Atlas

Estrogen Pathway Activity - TME-Stroma Atlas

Androgen Pathway Activity - TME-Immune Atlas

Estrogen Pathway Activity - TME-Immune Atlas

Figure S13

Alpha-beta T cell (Normal Liver atlas)

Central Venous LSEC (Normal Liver atlas)

Cholangiocyte (Normal Liver atlas)

Figure S13

Erythroid cell (Normal Liver atlas)

Gamma-delta T cell (Normal Liver atlas)

Hepatic stellate cell (Normal Liver atlas)

Figure S13

Hepatocyte (Normal Liver atlas)

Inflammatory macrophage (Normal Liver atlas)

Mature B cell (Normal Liver atlas)

Figure S13

NK-like cell (Normal Liver atlas)

Non-inflammatory macrophage (Normal Liver atlas)

Periportal liver sinusoidal endothelial cell (Normal Liver atlas)

Figure S13

Plasma cell (Normal Liver atlas)

Portal endothelial cell (Normal Liver atlas)

Figure S13

B cell (TME-Stroma atlas)

Cancer-associated fibroblast (TME-Stroma atlas)

Conventional dendritic cell 1 (TME-Stroma atlas)

Figure S13

Conventional dendritic cell 2 (TME-Stroma atlas)

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Hepatocyte (TME-Stroma atlas)

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Kunffer cell (TME-Stroma atlas)

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Figure S13

Liver sinusoidal endothelial cell (TME-Stroma atlas)

Liver vascular endothelial cell (TME-Stroma atlas)

Tumour liver vascular endothelial cell (TME-Stroma atlas)

Figure S13

Pericyte (TME-Stroma atlas)

Proliferation (TME-Stroma atlas)

Scar-associated macrophage (TME-Stroma atlas)

Figure S13

Stellate cell (TME-Stroma atlas)

T cell (TME-Stroma atlas)

Tissue macrophage (TME-Stroma atlas)

Figure S13

Vascular smooth muscle cell (TME-Stroma atlas)

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Figure S13

B cell (TME-Immune atlas)

Bi-potent cell (TME-Immune atlas)

CD4 positive T cell (TME-Immune atlas)

Figure S13

CD8 positive T cell (TME-Immune atlas)

Endothelial cell (TME-Immune atlas)

Fibroblast (TME-Immune atlas)

Figure S13

Hepatocyte (TME-Immune atlas)

Mast cell (TME-Immune atlas)

Myeloid cell (TME-Immune atlas)

Figure S13

NK cell (TME-Immune atlas)

Regulatory T cell (TME-Immune atlas)

